

Energy Transition Scenarios for Ecuador up to 2050: Modelling the Potential of Renewable Resources

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22 de mayo de 2026

Keywords: Climate variability , energy transition, energy diversification, Hydropower Solar photovoltaic (PV)

Acknowledgements

We would like to express their sincere gratitude to the training institution and organizers of the Energy Modelling Platform for Latin America and the Caribbean 2026 (EMP-LAC 26) for their guidance, technical support, and capacity-building activities that contributed to the development of this report. Special acknowledgment is extended to Climate Compatible Growth, International Centre for Theoretical Physics, World Bank Group, 2050 Pathways Platform, Universidad Politécnica Nacional, and the British Embassy Buenos Aires for organizing EMP-LAC 26 and promoting collaborative research on sustainable energy planning in the region. Also like to express their special appreciation to Fernando Plazas and Guillermo Fernandez for their valuable guidance, technical support, and mentorship throughout the training process and the development of this work.

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Executive Summary

Ecuador's electricity system relies heavily on hydropower (70-80%), creating significant vulnerability to climate variability and drought events. This study employs OSeMOSYS to evaluate the long-term evolution of the national electricity system under three scenarios Business-As-Usual (BAU), Hydro Reduction (DRO), and Least Cost (MIN) from 2022 to 2050.

Results show that electricity demand will grow steadily across all scenarios, from approximately 115 PJ in 2022 to over 255–265 PJ by 2050. Under the DRO scenario, a 43% reduction in hydropower capacity triggers a structural shift in the generation mix, with solar PV emerging as the dominant technology and total installed capacity exceeding 44 GW by 2050. A critical inflection point occurs when hydro capacity factor reductions surpass 25%, at which solar PV displaces hydropower as the primary source. These findings underscore the urgent need to diversify Ecuador's energy matrix through targeted policy action. Key recommendations include establishing progressive solar PV capacity targets, promoting renewable energy auctions, modernizing the grid, and developing regulatory frameworks for energy storage and flexible backup generation to ensure long-term energy security and climate resilience.

1. Introduction

In the context of Ecuador's energy sector, the electricity system relies heavily on hydropower generation, which accounts for approximately 75% of total electricity production, while the remaining share comes mainly from thermal sources, with only a

marginal contribution from non-conventional renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and biomass (Ministerio de Energía y Minas, 2024). This strong dependence on hydropower exposes the system to significant vulnerability to climate variability, particularly during droughts or dry seasons, when river flows in the main basins decrease and the effective hydropower generation capacity drops considerably.

In alignment with its NDC and climate commitments, Ecuador has established greenhouse gas mitigation objectives through the promotion of a more sustainable energy system, with an emphasis on energy efficiency and increasing the share of renewable energy sources (UNDP, 2020). In this context, the purpose of this study is to evaluate the long-term evolution of Ecuador's electricity system under alternative energy transition scenarios using OSeMOSYS. The analysis focuses on assessing the effects of gradually reducing hydropower dependence and increasing the participation of non-conventional renewable energy technologies such as solar, wind, geothermal, and biomass under future climate variability conditions.

2. Methodology

The Started Data Kit (SDK) developed under the EMP-LAC framework was used as the baseline model and calibrated with historical installed capacity and electricity generation data from 2022–2024. OSeMOSYS was selected for the long-term analysis of Ecuador's electricity system due to its capability to optimize the least-cost evolution of the energy system while considering technological, operational, and environmental constraints. The model was applied to evaluate scenarios aimed at reducing dependence on hydropower and increasing the integration of non-conventional renewable energy technologies, including solar, wind, geothermal, and biomass, under long-term climate variability conditions. (Howells *et al.*, 2011).

In this work were evaluated 3 scenarios, As shown in Figure 1:

- **Business-As-Usual (BAU)** simulates the evolution of the Ecuadorian electricity system without significant structural changes in the generation matrix or in renewable energy support policies.
- **Hydro Reduction (DRO)** For this specific scenario, a 43% reduction in the installed capacity of hydroelectric power plants was applied by comparing 2024 with 2022, according to the hydropower generation statistics. Similarly, studies conducted by the Central Bank of Ecuador and other researchers emphasize the urgency of carrying out an energy transition in Ecuador, where declining costs of non-conventional renewable energy technologies and regulatory advancements could diversify the energy matrix and reduce exposure to hydrological shocks and fossil fuel price volatility (wgaleas, 2025).
- **Least cost (MIN)** The least-cost scenario aims to identify the expansion pathway of the Ecuadorian electricity system capable of meeting projected demand at the lowest total investment and operational cost, without imposing strict constraints or specific subsidies on particular technologies.

Figure 1. Summary of scenarios explored in the modelling

3. Results

Figure 2. Electricity Annual Demand

As shown in figure 2, the projected annual electricity demand for 2022–2050 shows steady growth in all scenarios: BAU, DROUGHT (DRO), and Minimum Cost (MIN). In

2022, the electricity generation will be similar (about 115–117 PJ), dominated by hydroelectric generation. By 2030 it rises moderately to 140–145 PJ with little structural change. From 2040, scenarios diverge, with BAU reaching about 190 PJ and DRO/MIN near 195 PJ, as geothermal and off-grid solar gain share, especially in DRO. By 2050, BAU exceeds 255 PJ, DRO reaches 263 PJ with higher diversification, and MIN reaches 265 PJ, more concentrated in hydro and Solar Off-Grid; hydro remains the backbone in all cases.

Figure 3. Total Capacity

As shown in Figure 3, the total installed capacity follows different expansion paths by scenario. In 2022, capacity is about 7.5 GW, mainly hydro, with smaller shares of diesel, fuel oil, and biomass. By 2030 it reaches 8.5–10 GW, with DRO starting to add solar. From 2040, differences grow: BAU reaches about 11.5 GW and MIN around 12 GW in 2040, while DRO rises to nearly 25 GW on strong solar growth. By 2050 BAU settles near 18 GW, MIN at 17 GW, and DRO exceeds 44 GW, making solar the dominant technology. DRO thus entails a deep structural shift toward scalable renewables, especially solar, as the core of the 2050 energy transition.

Figure 4. Hydro FC Reduction – DRO scenario

As the reduction in the hydro capacity factor increases by 2050, the generation mix changes dramatically:

- 0%: The system is dominated entirely by Hydro (88%), with smaller shares from Onshore wind (5.5%) and Geothermal (5.4%). Solar PV is almost negligible (0.4%).
- 15%: Hydro still dominates (77.6%), but Solar PV begins to gain ground (8.6%), accompanied by Natural gas (2.1%) and small amounts of Oil products (0.4%).
- 25%: A critical inflection point. Solar PV (53.8%) displaces Hydro (31.4%) as the main source. The system undergoes a structural transition toward intermittent sources.
- 35%: Solar PV consolidates as the dominant source (54.4%), Hydro drops to 22%, and Natural gas grows notably to 8.1%, together with Oil products (4.2%) to cover intermittency.
- 43%: The structure stabilizes relative to 35%. Solar PV maintains its dominance (54.4%), Hydro continues to decline (19.3%), but Natural gas scales up to 10.8%

as flexible backup, highlighting the need for flexibility under higher solar penetration.

Figure 5. Hydro factor reduction - Installed capacity

The total installed capacity reflects a deep structural change as the reduction in the hydro capacity factor increases by 2050:

- 0%: The system is dominated by Hydro as the main technology, with a total capacity of just 17.1 GW. Solar PV has a modest presence, and the remaining technologies (Onshore wind, Geothermal, Oil products, Natural gas) occupy small fractions.
- 15%: Total capacity grows to 23.1 GW. Solar PV begins to gain significant ground, partially displacing Hydro, which remains relevant but is no longer dominant. The system starts to diversify.
- 25%: A breaking point. Total capacity nearly triples to 44.1 GW. Solar PV becomes the dominant technology, occupying the largest share. Hydro shrinks to a smaller fraction. This large jump in total capacity reflects the lower energy density of solar compared to hydro.
- 35%: The structure remains similar to 25%, with 43.7 GW in total. Solar PV consolidates its dominance, Hydro continues to decline, and the other technologies maintain small but stable shares.
- 43%: With 44.0 GW in total, the composition is practically identical to 35%. This suggests the system has reached a saturation point in substitution: further hydro reduction does not require additional solar capacity because the system was already oversized starting from 25%. However, it is worth noting a slight increase in the participation of flexible and complementary sources, particularly Natural gas, Onshore wind, Oil products, and Geothermal, reflecting the system's growing need for dispatchable backup and grid stability support under high solar penetration conditions.

5. Discussion

The modeling results reveal that Ecuador faces a structural transformation of its electricity system under any decarbonization scenario. The BAU scenario shows sustained reliance on existing hydroelectric generation and liquid fossil fuels, without meeting any climate targets. The MIN (minimum-cost) scenario demonstrates that carbon neutrality is technically achievable through a combination of hydro, Solar PV, onshore wind, and geothermal, always prioritizing the lowest-cost solution for the system. The DRO scenario is the most critical: there is a threshold between 15% and 25% reduction in the hydro capacity factor beyond which the system must be entirely reinvented, doubling total installed capacity and positioning Solar PV as the dominant technology. This shows that Ecuador cannot assume the reliability of its hydropower endowment under accelerated climate-change scenarios.

Ecuador's energy policy should prioritize long-term auctions for Solar PV and onshore wind that mobilize private investment through stable price signals. Geothermal energy represents a strategic opportunity as an emission-free, dispatchable baseload source and deserves active exploration through enabling regulatory frameworks. Given that under severe hydro stress natural gas takes on an increasingly important backup role, policy must anticipate this need by developing flexibility solutions—storage and regional interconnections—before they become urgent. The scale of the required transformation also demands preparing the industrial and education sectors to sustain the transition in terms of installed technical capacity within the country.

7. Conclusion

The results of this study highlight the need for Ecuador to advance toward an energy transition based on the diversification of its electricity matrix and the gradual reduction of hydropower dependence in order to reduce the system's vulnerability to climate variability and drought events. The reduced hydropower capacity factor scenario demonstrates that excessive reliance on hydropower generation represents a significant risk to long-term energy security, making it essential to strengthen public policies focused on the integration of non-conventional renewable energy technologies, particularly solar photovoltaic energy, complemented by wind and geothermal generation. Furthermore, the development of regulatory frameworks that promote energy storage, grid modernization, and renewable integration mechanisms will be crucial to ensuring system reliability.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted Technologies

During the preparation of this work, the authors used AI-assisted tools for language editing and clarity enhancement. The use of these tools did not affect the scientific content, data analysis, or conclusions of the study. The authors reviewed and validated the final manuscript and take full responsibility for its content.

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